

MODERN INTERACTIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING INTEGRATED SKILLS TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The research employs a blend of qualitative and quantitative approaches to examine the effectiveness of interactive teaching techniques in language training. Qualitative methods, such as interviews and observations, offer insights into subjective experiences, while quantitative methods, like test score analysis, provide measurable outcomes of these teaching techniques on language proficiency.*

The study begins by defining professional language proficiency and identifying the specific language skills required, forming the basis for selecting and designing targeted interactive teaching methods. Data is then collected from students undergoing professional language training, focusing on how effectively these techniques enhance their language proficiency and prepare them for their professional roles. The research also evaluates the students' ability to apply their acquired language skills in real-world professional contexts and describing interactive teaching methods that effectively develop language skills for future pilots. By aligning these methods with ICAO language proficiency requirements, the study ensures that the training provided is relevant and prepares students for their future careers.

Keywords: *interactive and engaging lessons, accessibility, innovation, group discussions.*

Uzbekistan is undergoing significant social modernization, industrialization, and innovative advancements as part of its integration into the global economy. The nation's primary goal is to rank among the top 30 developed countries worldwide. Achieving this ambition places immense responsibility on Uzbekistan's educators and youth to build national competitiveness, ensuring prosperity and global recognition. Learning foreign languages has become a critical priority in this context, particularly in fostering global engagement. Since gaining independence, Uzbekistan has implemented numerous initiatives to enhance youth education and knowledge. Each year, specific areas of focus are prioritized, and in 2021, physics and foreign languages were designated as key fields for development. Notably, foreign language instruction is now offered in 25 higher education institutions across the country, reflecting the nation's commitment to equipping its citizens with the skills necessary for international success.

Integrating technology into the classroom significantly enriches the educational experience by providing instant access to a wealth of information and resources. With devices like smartphones, tablets, and computers becoming integral to daily life, their use in education is both practical and beneficial. Technology enables teachers to design interactive and engaging lessons that maintain students' interest and active participation. Tools such as virtual classrooms extend learning opportunities beyond the traditional classroom setting, encouraging collaboration, discussion, and exploration. These digital platforms also foster a sense of community by enabling meaningful connections between students and teachers, enhancing shared learning experiences.

Apparently, teaching young learners requires special approaches to planning and organizing the educational process. Experts highlight “meaningful practice” which suggests “an activity where language control is still provided but where students are required to make

meaningful choices when carrying out practice” (Richards, 2006, p.16). Buhrow and Garcia (2006) recognize, that meaningful practice results in meaningful communication, because for kids, “learning is all about exploring their passions and interests” (p. VIII).

Technology facilitates differentiated instruction by addressing the varied needs of students through the use of diverse apps, software, and online tools. This allows teachers to tailor learning experiences to match individual abilities and interests, fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment where every student can thrive. Beyond improving classroom learning, technology equips students with essential skills for the digital age. In a world where digital literacy is crucial for success across nearly all professions, integrating technology into education helps students develop competencies such as information literacy, critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital citizenship, preparing them for future challenges.

However, it is important to note that technology should be used purposefully and thoughtfully in the classroom. It should complement and enhance teaching practices rather than replace them. Teachers need to be mindful of balancing screen time with other activities and ensuring that technology is used in a way that supports learning goals.

Integrating technology in the classroom is essential for fostering impactful learning experiences. It enables immediate access to information, encourages active participation, supports personalized instruction, and equips students with vital skills for navigating the digital era. By leveraging technological tools, educators can design engaging and inclusive environments that inspire students to achieve their maximum potential.

The acquisition of language proficiency for future pilots is considered to be one of the main targets of professional training. Here we should mention the main components of foreign language instruction goals: a) the acquisition of the knowledge of language skills for general communication use; b) exposing learners to other cultures and ideas; and c) fostering an appreciation of differences in cultures and ways of thinking. (Norris, 2006, p. 577).

Zimnjaja (2003) states that competence – is “an actual, formed personal quality as based on knowledge, intellectual and personally determined social-professional characteristics of an individual, his personal quality”.

Brainstorming has proven to be highly effective, as it aligns with children's natural inclination to play while simultaneously stimulating their creative thinking and enriching their active vocabulary. Among the activities tested, Talking Timebomb emerged as a favorite among both teachers and students due to its simplicity and minimal preparation requirements. The game begins with the teacher selecting a topic, playing a piece of music, and giving a ball to the students. The student holding the ball must say a word related to the topic before passing it to another. This continues until the music stops, at which point the student holding the ball is "out" and receives a "punishment"—speaking on the topic for at least 30 seconds. Notably, this activity is versatile and can be adapted to review not only vocabulary but also speech patterns or grammar structures, making it a valuable tool for language learning.

It should be noted that a teacher working with children deal with so-called mixed-ability groups. That is why a teacher has to take into consideration multiple intelligences of students: different types of personality, thinking, scope of attention, the ability to perceive and process information (Korovina, Pushkina, & Krivoshlykova, 2017, p.10).

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Interactive learning refers to an educational process that emphasizes the exchange and sharing of knowledge resources to foster innovation between an innovator, their suppliers, and clients. Rooted in a resource-based perspective, it incorporates competing and complementary theoretical frameworks, such as the complexity and organization of innovative activities and cross-sectoral technological interactions. Interactive learning is characterized by actively engaging learners in the educational journey, encouraging them to integrate their own experiences and insights into the process. It also involves learners in shaping and organizing their learning, making the process more dynamic and collaborative.

Interactive teaching styles are based on a simple principle: without practical application, students often fail to comprehend the depths of the study material. Interactive teaching is also beneficial for you as the teacher in a number of ways, including:

- a) measurable student accomplishments;
- b) flexibility in teaching;
- c) practice makes perfect;
- d) student motivation.

Incorporating interactive teaching methods: The study emphasizes the importance of using interactive teaching methods to enhance language training for future pilots. These methods include role-plays, simulations, group discussions, and real-life scenarios that simulate the communication challenges pilots may face in their professional roles.

“Role play is a way of bringing situations from real life into the classroom” (Doff 1990, 232). It may also include plays, dramas, sociodramas, and simulation. Here we use the general term role play for all of these types of activities, but we will also discuss the specific definitions, benefits, and uses of plays, dramas and sociodramas, and simulation in this section.

Role-playing exercises can be a valuable tool in language training for pilots, particularly for improving communication skills in realistic scenarios. For example, a role-play could involve a pilot and an air traffic controller interacting during a flight. The pilot would respond to the controller's instructions and inquiries using correct aviation language and terminology, allowing them to practice effective communication in a dynamic setting.

Similarly, simulations provide another effective method for language training. By replicating real-life situations, such as emergencies or adverse weather conditions, simulations enable pilots to develop both their language proficiency and decision-making skills under pressure. These interactive methods not only enhance language training but also prepare pilots for practical, real-world challenges.

Pilots must effectively communicate with both crew members and air traffic control, employing precise language and terminology. Practicing this in training helps them refine their language skills while managing the pressures of real-time decision-making. Additionally, group discussions offer aspiring pilots the chance to engage in meaningful conversations with peers and instructors on various aviation topics. These discussions not only enhance speaking and listening skills but also foster learning through the exchange of experiences and diverse perspectives.

Real-life scenarios can be created in the training environment to simulate the communication challenges that pilots may face in their professional roles. For example, future pilots may be given a scenario where they have to communicate with a non-English speaking passenger who requires assistance. This helps them develop their language skills in a practical and relevant context. Incorporating interactive teaching methods into language training for future pilots helps create a more engaging and effective learning experience. It allows them to practice their language skills in realistic scenarios, receive feedback on their performance, and develop the necessary communication skills required for their future careers as pilots.

Case Study is a deep and diagnostic study. It is acclaimed as a useful research technique. Many expert researchers in social sciences have assessed the importance of case study research. The following are some of the specific advantages of the case study: It helps to probe the entire life span of a social unit intensively and to analyze the complex factors that are influencing the social unit. Case data are vivid, absorbing and tend to reproduce a person's social attitudes and values. Case Study facilitates to understand everything about a social unit and the variety of habits, traits and qualities combined in a social unit. Case Study helps to secure a detailed information about the growth of the unit, group structure, individual life pattern etc. The relationship between individual and society is well brought out in the Case Study. Case Studies are indispensable for therapeutic and administrative purpose. It is also easy to generalize cases with the case and helps prepare a plan of action for treatment. Case Study is followed for comparison, classification, and analysis and for the formulation of hypothesis leading to further research.

In conclusion, these interactive teaching methods can be applied to foreign language teaching for future pilots as well. By incorporating principles of foreign language teaching, such as communicative language teaching and task-based learning, instructors can create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment.

Communicative language teaching focuses on developing students' ability to communicate effectively in real-life situations. In the context of language training for future pilots, this means providing opportunities for students to practice their language skills in realistic aviation scenarios. This could involve role plays, simulations, and group discussions, as mentioned earlier.

Task-based learning is another principle that can be applied to language training for future pilots. This approach emphasizes the importance of learning through meaningful tasks or activities. In the aviation context, this could involve giving students tasks that require them to use their language skills to complete a specific goal or objective. For example, students could be given a task to create a flight plan and present it to their peers or instructors using the appropriate aviation terminology.

By incorporating these principles into language training for future pilots, instructors can create a more interactive and effective learning experience. Students will have the opportunity to practice their language skills in realistic scenarios, receive feedback on their performance, and develop the necessary communication skills required for their future careers as pilots.

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